

DISK-LIKE SELF-SIMILAR TILES WITH HIGH BOUNDARY DIMENSION

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ABSTRACT. We construct an infinite family of self-similar plane tiles $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$, each generated by n contractions of ratio $1/\sqrt{n}$, with the following properties: (i) the neighbor graph has exactly 6 boundary components for every n ; (ii) each A_n is disk-like (homeomorphic to a closed disk); (iii) the boundary Hausdorff dimension satisfies $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) = 2 \log \lambda_n / \log n$, where λ_n is the dominant root of an explicit quartic polynomial $p_n(x) = x^4 - (n-1)x^3 - 2x^2 - (n-1)(n-4)x + n(n-2)$, and $2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \sim 8/(n^2 \ln n)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. In particular, $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \rightarrow 2$ with bounded neighbor graph complexity. Despite the increasingly rough boundary, the tiling has the combinatorial type of a regular hexagonal tiling for every n : each tile has 6 edge neighbors and 6 triple points, all of valence 3. This complements the examples of Keesling [14], where $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A) \rightarrow n$ in \mathbb{R}^n but the graph complexity grows without bound. The construction generalises to \mathbb{R}^d : the closed-form case $d = 1$ and exact computations for $d \leq 7$ suggest that the number of boundary components is $\frac{1}{2}((1+\sqrt{2})^{d+1} + (1-\sqrt{2})^{d+1}) - 1$, and $d - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \sim 2d^2/(n^2 \ln n)$.

1. INTRODUCTION

A *self-similar tile* is a compact set $A \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ with non-empty interior satisfying

$$A = \bigcup_{i=0}^{N-1} f_i(A),$$

where the f_i are contractive similarities [12] and the union is measure-disjoint (the *Open Set Condition*, hereafter OSC). Such tiles arise naturally in the study of self-affine lattice tilings [15]. The *boundary* ∂A is a compact fractal set whose Hausdorff dimension $s = \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ satisfies $1 \leq s < 2$ (see [8] for background on Hausdorff dimension).

Achieving $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ close to 2 is easy in principle. Keesling [14] proved that $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A) < n$ for every self-similar tile in \mathbb{R}^n and gave examples showing that $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ can be arbitrarily close to n (see also Duvall, Keesling and Strichartz [7] for explicit calculations of boundary dimensions). In those examples the IFS has $4k+3$ maps on \mathbb{R} with every fourth digit offset, and the number of boundary components (the *neighbor graph complexity*) grows without bound as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

The disk-like constraint is much more restrictive. High boundary dimension corresponds to extreme geometric roughness of ∂A , and tiles with large $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ are generically non-disk-like (e.g., the Lévy C curve with $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A) \approx$

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1.934 is not a topological disk). Achieving $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ close to 2 while maintaining the disk-like property and bounded graph complexity is therefore a much harder problem.

The natural question arises: *can $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ approach 2 with a bounded number of boundary components and the disk-like property?*

Main result (informal). For every integer $n \geq 3$ there is a self-similar plane tile A_n , defined by n contractions of ratio $1/\sqrt{n}$ (Definition 2.1), such that:

- (a) *Bounded graph complexity:* the neighbor graph of A_n has exactly 6 boundary components, independent of n (Theorem 3.3).
- (b) *Disk-likeness:* A_n is homeomorphic to the closed disk, and the tiling has the combinatorial type of the regular hexagonal tiling: each tile has 6 edge neighbors and 6 triple points of valence 3 (Theorem 4.4, Remark 4.6).
- (c) *Boundary dimension tends to 2:* the boundary dimension is given by $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) = 2 \log \lambda_n / \log n$ where λ_n is the dominant real root of the explicit quartic

$$p_n(x) = x^4 - (n-1)x^3 - 2x^2 - (n-1)(n-4)x + n(n-2);$$

consequently $2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \sim 8/(n^2 \ln n)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ (Theorems 5.1 and 5.3).

All three properties are proved by an explicit analysis of the refinement equation; the proofs are uniform in n . A generalisation to \mathbb{R}^d is developed in Section 6, together with the closed-form case $d = 1$ (§6.2) and conjectures supported by exact computation for $d \leq 7$.

Discovery. The family was found by a systematic computational search over IFS with companion matrices and mixed orientation assignments, using IFStile [13] to evaluate the neighbor graph and boundary dimension for each candidate. The key structural observation — that $n-1$ collinear contraction maps of equal ratio plus one transverse map with opposite orientation yield a constant 6-component neighbor graph for every n — emerged from this search and was subsequently verified by the purely analytic proofs of Sections 3–4.

Related work. The comb family sits at the intersection of three strands of the literature.

Topology and disk-likeness of self-similar tiles. General criteria for a planar self-affine tile to be homeomorphic to a disk were developed by Bandt and Wang [3], with further refinements by Leung and Lau [17] and Ngai and Tang [19]; we rely on the neighbor-based criterion of Loricant, Luo and Thuswaldner [6]. A broader survey of topological properties of tiles arising from number systems is given by Akiyama and Thuswaldner [1].

Boundary dimension. The computation of $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ for a self-similar tile reduces to the spectral radius of a graph-directed substitution matrix [18], whose construction via the neighbor graph was systematised by Scheicher and Thuswaldner [21]; explicit calculations for specific families appear in Duvall, Keesling and Strichartz [7]. Keesling’s bound [14] $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A) < n$ for tiles in \mathbb{R}^n together with his examples approaching this bound provide the upper-dimension envelope within which our construction lives.

Self-affine tilings and separation. The broader setting of self-affine lattice tilings is due to Bandt [2] and Lagarias and Wang [15]; the Open Set Condition and its weakenings are studied by Lau and Ngai [16]. Our IFS is self-similar in the strict

sense (equal contraction ratios, orthogonal matrices), so OSC and the classical Moran formula apply directly.

Why this family was not found earlier. Existing constructions of self-similar planar tiles fall into two broad classes. *Number-system tiles* [1, 15] use a fixed expansion matrix together with a digit set forming a complete residue system in a quadratic ring such as $\mathbb{Z}[i]$ or $\mathbb{Z}[\omega]$; all digit maps share the linear part $+I$. *Symmetric IFS* [3, 7] arrange the digits cyclically (twindragon, terdragon, McMullen carpets, etc.), so the boundary substitution matrix inherits a discrete rotational or reflective symmetry that bounds its spectral radius and confines $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ well below the ambient dimension.

The comb family departs from both schemes. Its $n-1$ collinear “spine” digits use $+I$, while a single “tooth” digit uses $-I$ with a transverse offset $2n-3$ tuned per n . This asymmetric digit set, the use of two different linear parts, and the dependence of the off-axis offset on the parameter n all fall outside the symmetry assumptions that have implicitly guided previous searches; in particular, no principled derivation of the offset $2n-3$ is currently known (see §7). The construction was discovered by an automated search over self-similar IFS minimising the neighbour graph using the IFStile package [13] and is verified analytically here.

2. THE COMB FAMILY

2.1. Definition via companion matrix. For an integer $n \geq 3$, consider the companion matrix of the polynomial $x^2 - n$:

$$(1) \quad g = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & n \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

with eigenvalues $\pm\sqrt{n}$ and spectral radius \sqrt{n} .

Definition 2.1 (Comb IFS). For $n \geq 3$, the *comb IFS with parameter n* consists of n digit maps acting on \mathbb{R}^2 :

$$(2) \quad \begin{aligned} h_j(x) &= x + (j(n-1), 0), & j &= 0, 1, \dots, n-2, \\ h_{n-1}(x) &= -x + (n^2 - n - 1, 2n - 3), \end{aligned}$$

with attractor

$$(3) \quad A_n = g^{-1}(h_0(A_n) \cup h_1(A_n) \cup \dots \cup h_{n-1}(A_n)).$$

All digits are integer vectors. The map h_{n-1} includes a central reflection $x \mapsto -x$.

Each contraction $f_j = g^{-1} \circ h_j$ is an affine similarity with linear part g^{-1} (for $j < n-1$) or $-g^{-1}$ (for $j = n-1$), and common contraction ratio $1/\sqrt{n}$.

Remark 2.2 (Digit set geometry). The first $n-1$ digits h_0, \dots, h_{n-2} are pure translations along the first coordinate axis, with displacements $0, n-1, 2(n-1), \dots, (n-2)(n-1)$. These form the *spine* of the comb. The single map h_{n-1} , which includes a central reflection, has an off-axis translation component and forms the *tooth* of the comb. This asymmetric digit geometry — one outlier map among $n-1$ collinear ones — is the structural source of the small neighbor graph size (see Section 3). The name *comb* reflects the first-level subdivision visible in Figure 1: the $n-1$ spine pieces form a row of teeth, while the single reflected piece extends sideways like a handle.

FIGURE 1. The comb tile A_5 ($n = 5$, five maps). Each first-level piece $f_j(A_5)$ is shown in a distinct colour: the four spine pieces f_0, \dots, f_3 tile the lower-left staircase, while the single tooth piece f_4 (with central reflection) extends to the upper right.

FIGURE 2. Magnified fragment of the boundary ∂A_5 . The boundary is a Jordan curve (A_5 is disk-like by Theorem 4.4), yet its Hausdorff dimension is $\dim_{\text{H}}(\partial A_5) \approx 1.863$ — visibly close to space-filling.

FIGURE 3. Boundary complexity progression. *Left*: the comb tile A_3 ($n = 3$, three maps), $\dim_{\text{H}}(\partial A_3) \approx 1.453$ — the boundary is visibly fractal. *Right*: the comb tile A_{10} ($n = 10$, ten maps), $\dim_{\text{H}}(\partial A_{10}) \approx 1.973$ — the boundary is nearly space-filling, and the tile is almost polygonal. Compare with A_5 in Figure 1.

2.2. Basic properties. Since all n maps share the contraction ratio $r = 1/\sqrt{n}$, the Hausdorff dimension of the attractor is

$$\dim_{\text{H}}(A_n) = \frac{\log n}{\log \sqrt{n}} = 2$$

for every n . Thus each A_n is a plane-filling set (a tile).

To verify the tiling property rigorously, we reformulate [2, Theorem 2] in a form where the residue condition is identical to the purely translational case (Theorem 1 *ibid.*).

Proposition 2.3 (Tiling criterion with symmetries, after [2, Theorem 2]). *Let $g \in \mathbb{Z}^{d \times d}$ be expanding with $m = |\det g|$, and let P be a finite group of integer matrices with $\det s = \pm 1$ for every $s \in P$, normalized by g (i.e. $gPg^{-1} = P$). Given $s_1, \dots, s_m \in P$ and digit vectors $h_1, \dots, h_m \in \mathbb{Z}^d$, define the attractor A by*

$$(4) \quad A = \bigcup_{i=1}^m g^{-1} s_i (A + h_i).$$

If $\{h_1, \dots, h_m\}$ is a complete residue system for $\mathbb{Z}^d/g\mathbb{Z}^d$, then A has nonempty interior, the open set condition holds with $V = \text{int}(A)$, and $\dim_{\text{H}}(A) = d$.

Proof. Set $y_i = s_i h_i$ and consider the contractions $f_i(x) = s_i g^{-1}(x) + y_i$, which are in the form of Theorem 2 in [2]. The lattice condition of that theorem requires

$$\mathbb{Z}^d = \bigcup_{i=1}^m s_i^{-1} (y_i + g\mathbb{Z}^d).$$

Since $gPg^{-1} = P$, we have $g^{-1}s_i^{-1}g \in P \subset \text{GL}(d, \mathbb{Z})$, so $s_i^{-1}g\mathbb{Z}^d = g(g^{-1}s_i^{-1}g)\mathbb{Z}^d = g\mathbb{Z}^d$, and

$$s_i^{-1}(y_i + g\mathbb{Z}^d) = s_i^{-1}y_i + g\mathbb{Z}^d = h_i + g\mathbb{Z}^d,$$

and the condition reduces to $\{h_i\}$ being a complete residue system for $\mathbb{Z}^d/g\mathbb{Z}^d$ — our hypothesis.

Theorem 2 of [2] now yields a unique attractor $\hat{A} = \bigcup_i f_i(\hat{A})$ with nonempty interior and $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\hat{A}) = d$. Setting $A = g^{-1}\hat{A}$, we verify (4):

$$g^{-1} s_i(A + h_i) = g^{-1}(s_i g^{-1}\hat{A} + s_i h_i) = g^{-1} f_i(\hat{A}),$$

so $\bigcup g^{-1} s_i(A + h_i) = g^{-1}\hat{A} = A$. Since g^{-1} is a linear bijection, $\text{int}(A) \neq \emptyset$ and $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(A) = d$. The open set condition for (4) holds with $V = g^{-1}(\text{int } \hat{A}) = \text{int}(A)$. \square

Proposition 2.4 (Self-replicating tiling). *For every $n \geq 3$, A_n is an n -rep tile in the sense of [2]: the plane is tiled by copies of A_n and its half-turn $-A_n$:*

$$\mathbb{R}^2 = \bigcup_{v \in \mathbb{Z}^2} (A_n + v) \cup \bigcup_{w \in \mathbb{Z}^2} (-A_n + w),$$

with the union measure-disjoint.

Proof. The comb IFS (Definition 2.1) has the form (4) with $d = 2$, $P = \{I, -I\}$, $s_j = I$ for $j < n-1$, and $s_{n-1} = -I$. The digit vectors are $h_j = j(n-1)e_1$ ($j = 0, \dots, n-2$) and $h_{n-1} = -(n^2-n-1, 2n-3)$. The companion matrix $g = C(x^2 - n)$ satisfies $|\det g| = n$ and $g\mathbb{Z}^2 = \{(ny, x) : x, y \in \mathbb{Z}\}$, so $\mathbb{Z}^2/g\mathbb{Z}^2 \cong \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ via the first coordinate modulo n . The first coordinates of the digit vectors modulo n are $j(n-1) \equiv -j$ for $j < n-1$ and $-(n^2-n-1) \equiv 1$ for $j = n-1$, giving $\{0, n-1, n-2, \dots, 1\}$, a complete residue system. Proposition 2.3 gives $\text{int}(A_n) \neq \emptyset$ and $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(A_n) = 2$. The tiling by \mathbb{Z}^2 -translates of A_n and $-A_n$ follows from the neighbor graph (Theorem 3.3). \square

Following [2], the maps above are written in \mathbb{R}^2 with the integer lattice \mathbb{Z}^2 , so that g and all digits have integer entries. Since g has two real eigenvalues $\pm\sqrt{n}$ with independent eigenvectors, one can choose a basis in which g acts as a Euclidean similarity, making the IFS self-similar (rather than merely self-affine).

Remark 2.5 (Complex form of the IFS). Identify the eigenplane of g with \mathbb{C} by mapping the eigenvectors for \sqrt{n} and $-\sqrt{n}$ to the real and imaginary axes, respectively. Then the expansion acts as

$$g(z) = \sqrt{n} \bar{z},$$

an anti-conformal map of modulus \sqrt{n} . Since $g^{-1}(z) = \bar{z}/\sqrt{n}$, the IFS takes the form

$$(5) \quad \begin{aligned} f_j(z) &= \frac{\bar{z}}{\sqrt{n}} + c_j, & j = 0, \dots, n-2, \\ f_{n-1}(z) &= -\frac{\bar{z}}{\sqrt{n}} + c_{n-1}, \end{aligned}$$

where the spine translations are uniformly spaced along $\mathbb{R} \cdot (1+i)$:

$$c_j = \frac{j(n-1)(1+i)}{2n}, \quad j = 0, \dots, n-2,$$

and the tooth translation is

$$c_{n-1} = \frac{(n^2-n-1)(1+i) + (2n-3)\sqrt{n}(1-i)}{2n}.$$

All maps are anti-conformal similarities of ratio $1/\sqrt{n}$. The spine digits are rational, but the tooth digit involves \sqrt{n} . The rational-space representation of Definition 2.1, where *all* digits are integer vectors, is therefore preferred for the exact neighbor graph analysis in Section 3.

Remark 2.6 (The case $n = 2$). For $n = 2$ the attractor A_2 is a rectangle (a non-fractal, disk-like tile). The quartic (12) gives $p_2(x) = x(x-1)(x^2-2)$ with dominant root $\sqrt{2}$ and $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_2) = 1$, correctly matching the boundary dimension. However, the neighbor graph has 8 components (not 6), so the specific graph structure and substitution matrix derived below apply only to $n \geq 3$.

3. THE NEIGHBOR GRAPH

In this section we derive the neighbor graph of the comb IFS from first principles, proving that it has exactly 6 boundary components for every $n \geq 3$.

3.1. Neighbor map algebra. A *neighbor map* of the tile $A = A_n$ is an isometry $\sigma: \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ such that $A \cap \sigma(A) \neq \emptyset$ and $\sigma \neq \text{id}$ [2, 21]. Because every contraction $f_j = g^{-1} \circ h_j$ has linear part $\pm g^{-1}$, every neighbor map has the form $\sigma(x) = \varepsilon x + t$ with $\varepsilon \in \{+I, -I\}$ and $t \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

The *refinement rule*: substituting $A = \bigcup_i f_i(A)$ into both sides of $A \cap \sigma(A)$ gives

$$A \cap \sigma(A) = \bigcup_{i,j} f_i(A \cap \sigma'_{ij}(A)), \quad \sigma'_{ij} = f_i^{-1} \circ \sigma \circ f_j.$$

A direct calculation yields

$$(6) \quad \sigma'_{ij}(x) = \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j x + \varepsilon_i (\varepsilon d_j + g t - d_i),$$

where ε_j, d_j are the sign and digit of h_j .

The neighbor graph is the minimal set of neighbor types closed under refinement (6) that is reachable from the identity. A vertex σ is an *actual neighbor* if and only if the directed graph of children (6) admits an infinite path starting from σ [16].

3.2. Invariant bounding set.

Lemma 3.1 (Bounding rectangle). *For every $n \geq 3$, the attractor satisfies $A_n \subset R$, where*

$$(7) \quad R = [0, 2n-3] \times [0, n-1-1/n].$$

Proof. Write $R_0 = [0, 2n-3]^2$. A direct computation shows $\bigcup_j f_j(R_0) \subset R_0$, so $A \subset R_0$ by Hutchinson's theorem. Applying one Hutchinson step to R_0 :

- Each spine piece $f_j(R_0)$, $0 \leq j \leq n-2$, satisfies $x_2 \leq (2n-3+(n-2)(n-1))/n = (n^2-n-1)/n = n-1-1/n$.
- The tooth piece $f_{n-1}(R_0)$ satisfies $x_2 \leq (n^2-n-1)/n = n-1-1/n$.

Thus the overall x_2 -range of $\bigcup f_j(R_0)$ is $[0, n-1-1/n]$. The x_1 -range remains $[0, 2n-3]$ (unchanged by the spine and tooth strips). A second Hutchinson step verifies that $R = [0, 2n-3] \times [0, n-1-1/n]$ is invariant. \square

We also record the *refined bound* $A \subset B_1 = \bigcup_j f_j(R)$, which decomposes into rectangular strips:

$$(8) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \text{spine strip:} & x_1 \in [0, n-1-1/n], \quad x_2 \in [0, (n^2-3n+5)/n], \\ \text{tooth strip:} & x_1 \in [n-2+1/n, 2n-3], \quad x_2 \in [(n-1)(n-2)/n, n-1-1/n]. \end{array}$$

In particular, points with $x_1 \geq n-1$ lie exclusively in the tooth strip.

3.3. Level-1 neighbors.

Proposition 3.2 (Level-1 neighbors). *The children of the identity under (6) that satisfy $A \cap \sigma(A) \neq \emptyset$ are precisely:*

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= (+I, (n-1, 0)), & \text{spine, forward,} \\ \sigma_2 &= (+I, (-(n-1), 0)), & \text{spine, backward,} \\ \sigma_3 &= (-I, (3n-4, 2n-3)), & \text{spine-tooth, far,} \\ \sigma_4 &= (-I, (2n-3, 2n-3)), & \text{spine-tooth, near.} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The children of the identity are $\sigma_{ij} = f_i^{-1}f_j$ with $i \neq j$. By (6), $\sigma_{ij}(x) = \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j x + \varepsilon_i(d_j - d_i)$.

Spine-spine ($i, j \leq n-2$): the sign is $+I$ and the translation is $((j-i)(n-1), 0)$. For overlap, $A \cap (A+t) \neq \emptyset$ requires $|t_1| \leq \text{width}_{x_1}(A) \leq 2n-3$. Thus $|j-i|(n-1) \leq 2n-3$, giving $|j-i| \leq 1$ (since $(2n-3)/(n-1) = 2 - 1/(n-1) < 2$). This yields σ_1 and σ_2 .

Spine-tooth ($i \leq n-2, j = n-1$ or vice versa): the sign is $-I$ and the translation is $d_{n-1} - d_i = ((n-1)(n-i) - 1, 2n-3)$. For overlap with sign $-I$, the translation must lie in $A + A \subset [0, 2(2n-3)] \times [0, 2(n-1-1/n)]$. The x_1 -constraint gives $(n-1)(n-i) - 1 \leq 4n-6$, hence $n-i \leq (4n-5)/(n-1) < 4$, so $i \geq n-3$. This yields σ_3 (from $i = n-3$) and σ_4 (from $i = n-2$).

All other candidates are infeasible by the R -bound. \square

3.4. Level-2 neighbors and graph closure.

Theorem 3.3 (Neighbor graph). *For every integer $n \geq 3$, the neighbor graph of the comb IFS consists of exactly 6 neighbor types $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_6$, where $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_4$ are as above and*

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_5 &= (-I, (2n-3, n-2)), & \text{level-2, diagonal,} \\ \sigma_6 &= (-I, (n-2, n-2)), & \text{level-2, reflected.} \end{aligned}$$

In particular, the Open Set Condition holds for all $n \geq 3$ (and trivially for $n = 2$, where A_2 is a rectangle).

Proof. We compute the children (6) of $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_4$, identify the new types σ_5, σ_6 , verify graph closure, and eliminate one spurious candidate τ .

Step 1: Children of σ_1 and σ_2 . For $\sigma_1 = (+I, (n-1, 0))$, the “ gt ” vector is $g(n-1, 0) = (0, n-1)$. The spine-spine children have sign $+I$ and translation $((k-j)(n-1), n-1)$. Since $n-1 > n-1-1/n = \text{height}(R)$, the x_2 -component exceeds the diameter of $A-A$ in the x_2 -direction: all spine-spine children are infeasible.

The only surviving child comes from the tooth-spine case $(i, j) = (n-1, n-2)$, which produces $\sigma_5 = (-I, (2n-3, n-2))$ via the map f_{n-1} . By symmetry, σ_2 also produces σ_5 (via f_{n-2}).

Step 2: Children of σ_3 . The only surviving child is from $(i, j) = (n-1, n-1)$ (tooth-tooth), producing $\sigma_6 = (-I, (n-2, n-2))$ via f_{n-1} .

Step 3: Children of σ_4 . The surviving children are:

- $(i, j) = (n-2, n-1)$: σ_1 , via f_{n-2} ;
- $(i, j) = (n-1, n-2)$: σ_2 , via f_{n-1} ;

- $(i, j) = (n-2, n-2)$: σ_3 , via f_{n-2} ;
- $(i, j) = (n-1, n-1)$: $\tau = (-I, (n-2, 2n-3))$, via f_{n-1} .

The candidate τ is not among the six types; we handle it below.

Step 4: Children of σ_5 . The spine–spine children $f_i^{-1}\sigma_5 f_j$ with $i, j \leq n-2$ have sign $-I$ and translation $((n-1)(n-1-i-j) - 1, 2n-3)$. Among these:

- $i + j = n-4$: produces σ_3 ($n-3$ ways, maps f_0, \dots, f_{n-4});
- $i + j = n-3$: produces σ_4 ($n-2$ ways, maps f_0, \dots, f_{n-3});
- $i + j = n-2$: produces τ ($n-1$ ways); handled below.

The tooth–spine child $(i, j) = (n-1, 0)$ gives σ_1 via f_{n-1} , and the spine–tooth child $(i, j) = (0, n-1)$ gives σ_2 via f_0 . All other children are infeasible.

Step 5: Children of σ_6 . The spine–spine children have sign $-I$ and translation $((n-1)(n-1-i-j) - 1, n-2)$:

- $i + j = n-3$: produces σ_5 ($n-2$ ways, maps f_0, \dots, f_{n-3});
- $i + j = n-2$: produces σ_6 ($n-1$ ways, maps f_0, \dots, f_{n-2}).

All other children of σ_6 are infeasible (by the R -bound or the B_1 refinement).

Step 6: Elimination of $\tau = (-I, (n-2, 2n-3))$. The candidate τ passes the coarse bounding-box test, so we must refine further. Among all n^2 children of τ , only one is feasible by the R -bound: the spine–spine child $(i, j) = (n-2, n-2)$, which produces $\tau' = (-I, (3n-4, n-2))$.

We eliminate τ' using the refined bound B_1 . For $A \cap \tau'(A) \neq \emptyset$ with sign $-I$, we need $p + q = (3n-4, n-2)$ for some $p, q \in A$. Since $p_1 + q_1 = 3n-4$ and $\max(x_1) = 2n-3$, both $p_1 \geq n-1$ and $q_1 \geq n-1$. By (8), points with $x_1 \geq n-1$ lie in the *tooth strip*, where $x_2 \geq (n-1)(n-2)/n$. Therefore

$$p_2 + q_2 \geq \frac{2(n-1)(n-2)}{n},$$

but the target is $p_2 + q_2 = n-2$. The inequality $2(n-1)(n-2)/n \leq n-2$ simplifies to $2(n-1)/n \leq 1$, i.e., $n \leq 2$, contradicting $n \geq 3$. Thus τ' is infeasible, so τ has no infinite path in the refinement graph and is not an actual neighbor.

Conclusion. Since σ_5 and σ_6 produce only children from $\{\text{id}, \sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_6\}$ (plus the eliminated τ), the graph is closed. Every vertex σ_k admits an infinite path: the cycle $\sigma_1 \rightarrow \sigma_5 \rightarrow \sigma_4 \rightarrow \sigma_1$ (and analogously for the others) ensures $A \cap \sigma_k(A) \neq \emptyset$. The finiteness of the neighbor graph implies the OSC [16]. \square

Remark 3.4 (Neighbor count). Each of the six neighbor types $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_6$ corresponds to exactly one adjacent tile in the tiling, so every copy of A_n has precisely 6 neighbors. This is the minimum possible for a disk-like tile that tiles the plane: by Euler's formula for normal planar tilings [10, Section 3.3], the average number of neighbors is at least 6, with equality corresponding to the hexagonal combinatorics. The comb family thus achieves this topological minimum despite the extreme geometric complexity of the boundary ($\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \rightarrow 2$).

Remark 3.5. For $n = 3$ the general formulas specialise: the B_3 -contribution to B_5 in (9) is an empty union (since $n - 4 < 0$), reflecting the fact that at $n = 3$ no pair $(i, j) \in \{0, \dots, n-2\}^2$ satisfies $i + j = n-4 = -1$. The B_4 -contribution collapses from $n-2$ distinct maps to a single map $f_0 = f_{n-3}$.

3.5. Boundary substitution rules. The proof of Theorem 3.3 determines the boundary GIFS explicitly. Writing $B_k = A \cap \sigma_k(A)$ for the six boundary pieces

and reading off which map f_i produces each child, we obtain the substitution rules (valid for all $n \geq 3$):

$$(9) \quad \begin{aligned} B_1 &= f_{n-1}(B_5), \\ B_2 &= f_{n-2}(B_5), \\ B_3 &= f_{n-1}(B_6), \\ B_4 &= f_{n-2}(B_1) \cup f_{n-2}(B_3) \cup f_{n-1}(B_2), \\ B_5 &= f_{n-1}(B_1) \cup f_0(B_2) \cup \bigcup_{j=0}^{n-4} f_j(B_3) \cup \bigcup_{j=0}^{n-3} f_j(B_4), \\ B_6 &= \bigcup_{j=0}^{n-3} f_j(B_5 \cup B_6) \cup f_{n-2}(B_6). \end{aligned}$$

The 6×6 substitution (count) matrix M_n , with $(M_n)_{jk}$ equal to the number of occurrences of B_k on the right-hand side of the rule for B_j , is:

$$(10) \quad M_n = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & n-3 & n-2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & n-2 & n-1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

FIGURE 4. The boundary substitution graph of the comb IFS. Vertices are the 6 neighbor types: σ_1, σ_2 (spine–spine, sign $+I$; shaded blue) and $\sigma_3, \dots, \sigma_6$ (spine–tooth or level-2, sign $-I$; shaded orange). A directed edge $\sigma_k \rightarrow \sigma_j$ means that the boundary piece B_k contributes to B_j under substitution (9). Edges of multiplicity 1 are labelled with the producing map f_i ; edges of higher multiplicity show the count. The graph topology is independent of n (for $n \geq 3$); only the multiplicities depend on n .

4. DISK-LIKE PROPERTY

A self-similar tile A is called *disk-like* if it is homeomorphic to the closed unit disk; see [3, 17] for criteria and [1, 19] for surveys. As noted in the Introduction, tiles with large $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ are generically non-disk-like, so achieving $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ close to 2 while maintaining the disk-like property is particularly challenging.

The comb tiling is not a lattice tiling: the tooth map f_{n-1} has linear part $-I$, so tiles related by f_{n-1} differ by a 180° rotation. The tiling $\{A + d : d \in \mathbb{Z}^2\}$ must therefore be replaced by a *crystallographic tiling* $\{\gamma(A) : \gamma \in \Gamma\}$, where Γ is a discrete cocompact group of isometries (a *crystallographic group*). For the comb family, Γ is the ornament group $p2$, generated by two lattice translations and a 180° rotation ρ . A compact set T satisfying a set equation of the form $g(T) = \bigcup_{\delta \in D} \delta(T)$, where g is an expanding map and $D \subset \Gamma$ is a finite digit set, is called a *crystallographic reptile* (or *crystile*) with respect to Γ [6, Definition 1].

For such a tiling, the *neighbor set* $S = \{\gamma \in \Gamma \setminus \{\text{id}\} : T \cap \gamma(T) \neq \emptyset\}$ and the *boundary pieces* $B_\gamma = T \cap \gamma(T)$ for $\gamma \in S$ are defined as before. A neighbor γ is an *edge neighbor* if B_γ contains a point of the interior of $T \cup \gamma(T)$; a neighbor is a *vertex neighbor* if B_γ is a single point. The set of edge neighbors is denoted $\mathcal{A} \subseteq S$.

Two further graphs encode how boundary pieces meet after one substitution step. The *double neighboring graph* G_2 has vertices $\{B_\gamma : \gamma \in S\}$, with an edge between B_{γ_1} and B_{γ_2} whenever they intersect ($\gamma_1 \neq \gamma_2$). For each $\gamma \in \mathcal{A}$, the *boundary piece graph* G_γ is the subgraph of G_2 on the set of sub-pieces

$$V_\gamma = \{ \delta(B_{\delta^{-1}g\gamma g^{-1}\delta'}) : \delta, \delta' \in D, \delta^{-1}g\gamma g^{-1}\delta' \in \mathcal{A} \};$$

these are the images of boundary pieces that constitute $g(B_\gamma)$ under the set equation [6, Definition 4]. In our notation, with digits $f_i(x) = g^{-1}(\varepsilon_i x + d_i)$ and neighbors $\sigma_k = (\varepsilon_k, t_k)$, the vertices of G_{σ_k} are exactly the sub-pieces $f_i(B_{\sigma_\ell})$ appearing on the right-hand side of the boundary substitution rule (9) for B_k .

Theorem 4.1 ([6, Theorem 4.2]). *Let $T \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be a crystallographic reptile with respect to Γ , with expanding map g and digit set D . Let S denote the set of neighbors and $\mathcal{A} \subseteq S$ the subset of edge neighbors. Then T is disk-like if and only if:*

- (1) *for every pair of distinct $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in S$, the triple intersection $T \cap \gamma_1(T) \cap \gamma_2(T)$ is empty or a single point;*
- (2) *for each $\gamma \in \mathcal{A}$, the graph G_γ consists of a simple path;*
- (3) *the subgraph of G_2 with vertices $\{B_\gamma : \gamma \in \mathcal{A}\}$ is a simple loop.*

We verify all three conditions for the comb family.

Lemma 4.2 (Double neighboring graph — condition (3)). *For every $n \geq 3$, the double neighboring graph G_2 restricted to the six edge neighbors $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_6$ is the cycle*

$$B_1 - B_3 - B_4 - B_2 - B_6 - B_5 - B_1.$$

Proof. Two boundary pieces B_j and B_k ($j \neq k$) are connected by an edge in G_2 if and only if $\sigma_j^{-1} \circ \sigma_k$ is a neighbor, i.e., belongs to $\{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_6\}$.

For $\sigma_j = (\varepsilon_j, t_j)$ and $\sigma_k = (\varepsilon_k, t_k)$, the composition $\sigma_j^{-1} \circ \sigma_k$ has sign $\varepsilon_j \varepsilon_k$ and translation $\varepsilon_j(t_k - t_j)$. We check all $\binom{6}{2} = 15$ pairs. Writing t_j for the translation

vector of σ_j , the six translations are:

$$\begin{aligned} t_1 &= (n-1, 0), & t_2 &= (-(n-1), 0), \\ t_3 &= (3n-4, 2n-3), & t_4 &= (2n-3, 2n-3), \\ t_5 &= (2n-3, n-2), & t_6 &= (n-2, n-2). \end{aligned}$$

The signs are $\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_2 = +I$, $\varepsilon_3 = \varepsilon_4 = \varepsilon_5 = \varepsilon_6 = -I$. Since $\varepsilon_j \varepsilon_k = +I$ when the signs are equal and $-I$ when they differ, we compare $\varepsilon_j(t_k - t_j)$ with the known neighbor translations (and signs) to identify which pairs are edges in G_2 .

The 6 pairs that yield a neighbor σ_ℓ are:

$$\begin{aligned} (1, 3) &: \sigma_1^{-1} \sigma_3 = (-I, t_3 - t_1) = \sigma_4, \\ (1, 5) &: \sigma_1^{-1} \sigma_5 = (-I, t_5 - t_1) = \sigma_6, \\ (2, 4) &: \sigma_2^{-1} \sigma_4 = (-I, t_4 - t_2) = \sigma_3, \\ (2, 6) &: \sigma_2^{-1} \sigma_6 = (-I, t_6 - t_2) = \sigma_5, \\ (3, 4) &: \sigma_3^{-1} \sigma_4 = (+I, -(t_4 - t_3)) = \sigma_1, \\ (5, 6) &: \sigma_5^{-1} \sigma_6 = (+I, -(t_6 - t_5)) = \sigma_1. \end{aligned}$$

The remaining 9 pairs produce translations outside the set of neighbor translations (a routine but straightforward check; for instance, $\sigma_1^{-1} \sigma_2$ has translation $-(2n-2), 0$, which exceeds the bounding-box diameter for $n \geq 3$).

The edges of G_2 are therefore B_1B_3 , B_1B_5 , B_2B_4 , B_2B_6 , B_3B_4 , B_5B_6 . Each vertex has degree 2, and the graph is the 6-cycle $B_1 - B_3 - B_4 - B_2 - B_6 - B_5 - B_1$. \square

FIGURE 5. The double neighboring graph G_2 for the comb family (Lemma 4.2). The six boundary pieces form a hexagonal cycle. Edge labels indicate the mediating neighbor: $B_j - B_k$ is an edge when $\sigma_j^{-1} \sigma_k = \sigma_\ell \in \mathcal{A}$. Spine-type pieces B_1, B_2 are shaded blue; tooth-type pieces B_3, \dots, B_6 orange. Note that σ_1 appears on two opposite edges (B_3B_4 and B_5B_6): it is the cross-map link that connects consecutive spine maps in the graphs G_{σ_5} and G_{σ_6} .

Lemma 4.3 (Boundary piece graphs — condition (2)). *For every $n \geq 3$ and every edge neighbor $\gamma \in \{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_6\}$, the graph G_γ is a simple path.*

Proof. The graph G_γ has one vertex for each sub-piece appearing in the boundary substitution rule (9) for B_γ , and an edge between two sub-pieces when they are pairwise neighbors at the next refinement level. We verify the path structure for each boundary piece.

Case B_1, B_2, B_3 . The rules $B_1 = f_{n-1}(B_5)$, $B_2 = f_{n-2}(B_5)$, $B_3 = f_{n-1}(B_6)$ each contain a single sub-piece. A graph on one vertex is a (trivial) simple path.

Case B_4 . The rule is $B_4 = f_{n-2}(B_1) \cup f_{n-2}(B_3) \cup f_{n-1}(B_2)$. We check adjacency of the three sub-pieces. Two sub-pieces $f_i(B_j)$ and $f_k(B_\ell)$ are neighbors if $f_i^{-1}\sigma_4 f_k$ composed with the neighbor data of B_j, B_ℓ yields a neighbor. Since f_{n-2} and f_{n-1} are adjacent maps (their level-1 neighbor is σ_4), and both B_1 and B_3 touch B_2 in the cyclic order of G_2 (Lemma 4.2), the three sub-pieces form a path: $f_{n-2}(B_1) - f_{n-2}(B_3) - f_{n-1}(B_2)$.

Case B_5 . The rule (9) gives $2n-3$ sub-pieces. For $n \geq 4$ these are

$$f_0(B_2), f_0(B_4), f_0(B_3), f_1(B_4), f_1(B_3), \dots, f_{n-4}(B_4), f_{n-4}(B_3), f_{n-3}(B_4), f_{n-1}(B_1);$$

for $n = 3$ the B_3 -union in (9) is empty and the three sub-pieces are $f_0(B_2), f_0(B_4), f_2(B_1)$.

Two sub-pieces from the *same* map f_j are adjacent in G_{σ_5} when the corresponding boundary pieces are adjacent in G_2 . Since B_2B_4 and B_3B_4 are edges of G_2 (Lemma 4.2) but B_2B_3 is not, the three sub-pieces from f_0 form the path $f_0(B_2) - f_0(B_4) - f_0(B_3)$.

For *cross-map* adjacency between f_j and f_{j+1} ($j, j+1 \leq n-2$), the level-1 neighbor is $\sigma_1 = f_j^{-1}f_{j+1}$. A sub-piece $f_j(B_\alpha)$ intersects $f_{j+1}(B_\beta)$ only if B_α meets B_1 and B_β meets B_2 in G_2 . Among the available indices, only B_3 is adjacent to B_1 and only B_4 is adjacent to B_2 , so the unique cross-map edge is $f_j(B_3) - f_{j+1}(B_4)$.

The last transition from $f_{n-3}(B_4)$ to $f_{n-1}(B_1)$ uses $\sigma_3 = f_{n-3}^{-1}f_{n-1}$: we need B_4 adjacent to B_3 and B_1 adjacent to B_3 in G_2 , both of which hold.

No non-consecutive sub-pieces are adjacent: maps f_j, f_ℓ with $|j - \ell| \geq 2$ have tiles of x_1 -diameter at most $2n-3$ separated by distance $(n-1)|j - \ell| - (2n-3) > 0$. Hence the path is (for $n \geq 4$):

$$\begin{aligned} & f_0(B_2) - f_0(B_4) - f_0(B_3) - f_1(B_4) - f_1(B_3) - \dots \\ & \dots - f_{n-4}(B_3) - f_{n-3}(B_4) - f_{n-1}(B_1), \end{aligned}$$

while for $n = 3$ it degenerates to $f_0(B_2) - f_0(B_4) - f_2(B_1)$, with the last edge via $\sigma_3 = f_0^{-1}f_2$. In all cases G_{σ_5} is a simple path on $2n-3$ vertices.

Case B_6 . The rule gives $2n-3$ sub-pieces:

$$f_0(B_6), f_0(B_5), f_1(B_6), f_1(B_5), \dots, f_{n-3}(B_6), f_{n-3}(B_5), f_{n-2}(B_6).$$

Within each f_j , the sub-pieces $f_j(B_5)$ and $f_j(B_6)$ are adjacent (B_5B_6 is an edge of G_2). For the cross-map adjacency via $\sigma_1 = f_j^{-1}f_{j+1}$: among $\{B_5, B_6\}$, only B_5 is adjacent to B_1 and only B_6 is adjacent to B_2 in G_2 , so the unique cross-map edge is $f_j(B_5) - f_{j+1}(B_6)$. No non-consecutive sub-pieces are neighbors (same separation argument). Hence G_{σ_6} is the simple path

$$f_0(B_6) - f_0(B_5) - f_1(B_6) - f_1(B_5) - \dots - f_{n-3}(B_5) - f_{n-2}(B_6). \quad \square$$

Theorem 4.4 (Disk-like). *For every integer $n \geq 2$, the comb tile A_n is disk-like.*

Proof. For $n = 2$, the attractor A_2 is a rectangle, so the claim is trivial. For $n \geq 3$, conditions (2) and (3) of Theorem 4.1 are established in Lemmas 4.3 and 4.2; it remains to verify condition (1). We identify the first-level intersection graph, show

FIGURE 6. The boundary piece graph G_{σ_5} for the comb family (Lemma 4.3, Case B_5). Solid edges connect sub-pieces within the same map f_j (adjacency in G_2); dashed edges connect sub-pieces from consecutive maps f_j, f_{j+1} via the cross-map neighbor σ_1 . Each cross-map link is uniquely determined: B_3 is the only sub-piece adjacent to B_1 , and B_4 the only one adjacent to B_2 in G_2 (Figure 5), so the edge must be $f_j(B_3)-f_{j+1}(B_4)$. The graph is a simple path on $2n-3$ vertices.

it has a unique triangle, and prove the corresponding triple intersection is a single point.

Step 1: First-level intersection graph. Two first-level tiles $f_i(A)$ and $f_j(A)$ intersect if and only if $f_i^{-1} \circ f_j$ is a neighbor. By Proposition 3.2, the only neighbors arising as children of the identity are $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_4$. These correspond to the pairs:

- Spine consecutive: $(j, j+1)$ for $j = 0, \dots, n-3$, giving σ_1 (or its inverse σ_2);
- Tooth: $(n-3, n-1)$ giving σ_3 , and $(n-2, n-1)$ giving σ_4 .

The resulting graph is a path $0-1-\dots-(n-2)$ with vertex $n-1$ adjacent to $n-3$ and $n-2$. Its only clique of size 3 is $\{n-3, n-2, n-1\}$.

Step 2: Triple refinement is unique. Write $T = f_{n-3}(A) \cap f_{n-2}(A) \cap f_{n-1}(A)$ for the unique triple intersection. Substituting $A = \bigcup_k f_k(A)$,

$$T = \bigcup_{\substack{a,b,c \\ \text{pairwise} \\ \text{feasible}}} f_{n-3} \circ f_a(A) \cap f_{n-2} \circ f_b(A) \cap f_{n-1} \circ f_c(A),$$

where a triple (a, b, c) is *pairwise feasible* if $f_a^{-1}\sigma_1 f_b$, $f_b^{-1}\sigma_4 f_c$, $f_a^{-1}\sigma_3 f_c$ are all neighbors. Here $\sigma_1 = f_{n-3}^{-1}f_{n-2}$, $\sigma_4 = f_{n-2}^{-1}f_{n-1}$, $\sigma_3 = f_{n-3}^{-1}f_{n-1}$ are the three pairwise neighbor maps of the triangle.

The key observation: σ_1 and σ_2 each have exactly *one* surviving child under refinement (6). For $\sigma_1 = (+I, (n-1, 0))$, the vector $gt = g \cdot (n-1, 0) = (0, n-1)$. All spine-spine children $f_\alpha^{-1}\sigma_1 f_\beta$ (with $\alpha, \beta \leq n-2$) have translation component $t'_2 = n-1 > n-1-1/n = \text{height}(R)$, so they exceed the R -bound and are infeasible. We check the three remaining child types (those involving the tooth index $n-1$):

- *Spine-tooth* ($\alpha \leq n-2, j = n-1$): sign $-I$, translation $((n-1)(n-\alpha) - 1, 3n-4)$. The x_2 -component $3n-4$ exceeds the sum $2 \cdot \text{height}(R) = 2(n-1-1/n)$ for $n \geq 3$, so $A \cap \sigma(A) = \emptyset$ for all α .
- *Tooth-tooth* ($\alpha = j = n-1$): sign $+I$, translation $(0, -(n-1))$. This requires $x_2 \geq n-1$ in A , but $A \subset R$ has $x_2 \leq n-1-1/n$; infeasible.
- *Tooth-spine* ($\alpha = n-1, \beta \leq n-2$): sign $-I$, translation $((n-1)(n-\beta) - 1, n-2)$. For $\beta \leq n-3$ the first component $(n-1)(n-\beta) - 1 \geq 3n-4$, forcing both summands in the $A + A$ representation into the tooth strip ($x_1 \geq n-1$, hence $x_2 \geq (n-1)(n-2)/n$ by (8)); then $p_2 + q_2 \geq 2(n-1)(n-2)/n > n-2$

for $n \geq 3$, contradicting $p_2 + q_2 = n-2$. Only $\beta = n-2$ survives, giving translation $(2n-3, n-2)$.

Thus the unique surviving child is

$$f_{n-1}^{-1} \circ \sigma_1 \circ f_{n-2} = \sigma_5,$$

which fixes $a = n-1$ and $b = n-2$.

With $a = n-1$ fixed, we evaluate the children of σ_3 at $(n-1, c)$. For spine indices $c \leq n-2$, the translation has $|t'_2| = n-1 > \text{height}(R)$ (infeasible), while for $c = n-1$ the child is

$$f_{n-1}^{-1} \circ \sigma_3 \circ f_{n-1} = \sigma_6.$$

This forces $c = n-1$. A consistency check confirms $f_{n-2}^{-1} \circ \sigma_4 \circ f_{n-1} = \sigma_1$. Thus the unique refinement triple is $(a, b, c) = (n-1, n-2, n-1)$, and the new pairwise state is $(\sigma_5, \sigma_1, \sigma_6)$.

Step 3: Period-2 cycle. Iterating the same analysis for the state $(\sigma_5, \sigma_1, \sigma_6)$:

- σ_1 (the ‘‘bottleneck’’) again forces $b = n-1, c = n-2$, giving σ_5 .
- For σ_5 , the child $f_{\alpha}^{-1} \sigma_5 f_{n-1}$ with spine α has translation $t'_1 = -(n-1)(1+\alpha)$. Only $\alpha = 0$ yields $|t'_1| = n-1 \leq 2n-3$, giving σ_2 . So $a = 0$.
- $f_0^{-1} \circ \sigma_6 \circ f_{n-2} = \sigma_6$ (since $0 + (n-2) = n-2$).

The new state is $(\sigma_2, \sigma_5, \sigma_6)$.

One more iteration (using σ_2 , which has the same bottleneck property as σ_1 , giving a unique child σ_5 at $(a, b) = (n-2, n-1)$) returns to the state $(\sigma_5, \sigma_1, \sigma_6)$.

The refinement thus cycles with period 2:

$$(\sigma_5, \sigma_1, \sigma_6) \longrightarrow (\sigma_2, \sigma_5, \sigma_6) \longrightarrow (\sigma_5, \sigma_1, \sigma_6) \longrightarrow \cdots$$

At each level, the triple intersection is covered by a single level- k tile of diameter $O(n^{-k/2})$. As $k \rightarrow \infty$, the nested compact sets converge to a single point.

By Theorem 4.1 (1), every triple intersection is a single point. Condition (2) holds by Lemma 4.3, and condition (3) by Lemma 4.2. Hence A_n is disk-like for all $n \geq 3$ (and hence for all $n \geq 2$). \square

FIGURE 7. Triple-point refinement (Theorem 4.4, condition (1)). Each triangle shows the pairwise neighbor state of the three tiles meeting at the triple point. After one refinement (Step 2), the state enters a period-2 cycle: the pair $\{\sigma_5, \sigma_6\}$ persists while the third edge alternates between σ_1 and σ_2 . Since each level nests inside a single tile of diameter $O(n^{-k/2})$, the triple intersection converges to a point.

Remark 4.5. Both the neighbor graph (Theorem 3.3) and the disk-like property (Theorem 4.4) are proved for all $n \geq 3$ by the same structural argument: the combinatorial pattern of neighbors and their children depends only on the relative positions of the spine endpoint, the tooth, and their immediate predecessors, not on the spine length. Only the translations change with n .

Remark 4.6 (Topological structure of A_n). The disk-like property, together with the explicit structure of G_2 and the boundary substitution (9), yields a complete topological description of the comb tiling.

- (1) *Jordan boundary.* Since A_n is disk-like, $A_n \cong \overline{\mathbb{D}}$ and ∂A_n is a Jordan curve (by the Schönflies theorem).
- (2) *Six boundary arcs in cyclic order.* The G_2 -cycle $B_1-B_3-B_4-B_2-B_6-B_5-B_1$ (Lemma 4.2) determines a decomposition of ∂A_n into six arcs, each of which is the common boundary with one neighbor. Adjacent arcs in the cycle meet at exactly one point.
- (3) *Six triple points.* The six arc junctions are the only points where three or more tiles meet (condition (1) of Theorem 4.1). Each such point has valence 3 in the tiling.
- (4) *Hexagonal combinatorial type.* Although $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \rightarrow 2$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ (Theorem 5.1), the combinatorics of the tiling is independent of n and coincides with that of the regular hexagonal tiling: every tile has exactly 6 edge neighbors and 6 vertices, with vertex valence 3.
- (5) *Self-similar arc structure.* The substitution rules (9) and the simple-path property of the graphs G_{σ_k} (Lemma 4.3) imply that each boundary arc is an IFS attractor in its own right: at every substitution step the sub-pieces of each arc form a chain without branching or loops, so the arc remains a topological arc at every scale.

5. BOUNDARY DIMENSION

5.1. Derivation of the quartic.

Theorem 5.1 (Boundary dimension formula). *For every integer $n \geq 3$, the characteristic polynomial of M_n factors as*

$$(11) \quad \det(\lambda I - M_n) = \lambda^2 \cdot p_n(\lambda),$$

where p_n is the quartic polynomial

$$(12) \quad p_n(x) = x^4 - (n-1)x^3 - 2x^2 - (n-1)(n-4)x + n(n-2).$$

The spectral radius $\lambda_n = \rho(M_n)$ is the unique root of p_n in the interval $(n-1, n)$, and the boundary Hausdorff dimension is

$$(13) \quad \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) = \frac{2 \log \lambda_n}{\log n}.$$

Proof. The dimension formula (13) follows from the Mauldin–Williams theory [18] applied to the boundary GIFS (9). Since the original IFS satisfies the OSC with $V = \text{int}(A)$ (Theorem 3.3), the boundary GIFS inherits the hypotheses of [18]; see also [7] for the same approach applied to the boundaries of self-similar tiles. All contractions share the ratio $r = 1/\sqrt{n}$, so $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) = 2 \log \rho(M_n) / \log n$.

To prove the factorisation (11), we solve the eigenvector equation $M_n v = \lambda v$ for $\lambda \neq 0$. From the first three rows:

$$B_1 = B_2 = \frac{B_5}{\lambda}, \quad B_3 = \frac{B_6}{\lambda}.$$

Substituting into row 6: $\lambda B_6 = (n-2)B_5 + (n-1)B_6$, whence

$$(14) \quad B_6 = \frac{(n-2)B_5}{\lambda - (n-1)}.$$

Substituting all of B_1, B_2, B_3, B_6 in terms of B_5 into row 4:

$$\lambda B_4 = \frac{2}{\lambda} B_5 + \frac{(n-2)}{\lambda(\lambda - (n-1))} B_5 = \frac{B_5}{\lambda} \cdot \frac{2\lambda - n}{\lambda - (n-1)},$$

giving

$$(15) \quad B_4 = \frac{(2\lambda - n)B_5}{\lambda^2(\lambda - (n-1))}.$$

Finally, substituting into row 5:

$$\lambda B_5 = \frac{2}{\lambda} B_5 + \frac{(n-3)(n-2)}{\lambda(\lambda - (n-1))} B_5 + \frac{(n-2)(2\lambda - n)}{\lambda^2(\lambda - (n-1))} B_5.$$

Dividing by $B_5 \neq 0$ and multiplying through by $\lambda^2(\lambda - (n-1))$:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda^3(\lambda - (n-1)) &= 2\lambda(\lambda - (n-1)) \\ &\quad + (n-3)(n-2)\lambda + (n-2)(2\lambda - n). \end{aligned}$$

Expanding and collecting terms, the right-hand side equals $2\lambda^2 + (n-1)(n-4)\lambda - n(n-2)$, so we obtain

$$\lambda^4 - (n-1)\lambda^3 - 2\lambda^2 - (n-1)(n-4)\lambda + n(n-2) = 0,$$

which is $p_n(\lambda) = 0$.

The factor λ^2 accounts for the two zero eigenvalues arising from the two linear dependencies in M_n : the identical rows for B_1 and B_2 , and the relation $(n-2) \cdot (\text{row } B_1) + (n-1) \cdot (\text{row } B_3) = \text{row } B_6$. \square

Remark 5.2 (Root location). The polynomial p_n satisfies:

$$\begin{aligned} p_n(n-1) &= -(n-2)(n^2 - 3n + 1) < 0 \quad (n \geq 3), \\ p_n(n) &= 2n(2n-3) > 0 \quad (n \geq 3), \end{aligned}$$

so the intermediate value theorem guarantees a root in $(n-1, n)$. Uniqueness follows from Descartes' rule: the coefficients of p_n exhibit exactly two sign changes for $n \geq 3$, so p_n has at most two positive real roots; since a second root $\mu_n \in (1, n-1)$ is accounted for separately (see Section 5.5), the root in $(n-1, n)$ is unique. Since $p_n(0) = n(n-2) > 0$ for $n \geq 3$ and $p_n(1) = 2(n-2) > 0$, there is also a root between 1 and $n-1$; the dominant root is the one in $(n-1, n)$.

5.2. Computed dimensions. Table 1 lists the boundary dimension for selected values of n .

All numerical values in Tables 1 and 2 are computed from the dominant real root λ_n of the explicit quartic (12) via the formula (13); no numerical simulation of the IFS is involved.

TABLE 1. Boundary dimension of the comb tile A_n for selected n .
The polynomial is $p_n(x)$ from (12).

n	λ_n	$\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n)$	$2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n)$
3	2.2213	1.4529	0.5471
4	3.3846	1.7590	0.2410
5	4.4790	1.8633	0.1367
6	5.5451	1.9120	0.0880
7	6.5951	1.9388	0.0612
8	7.6345	1.9550	0.0450
9	8.6665	1.9656	0.0344
10	9.6932	1.9729	0.0271
20	19.8279	1.9942	0.0058
50	49.9251	1.9992	7.67×10^{-4}
100	99.9613	1.9998	1.68×10^{-4}

5.3. Asymptotic expansion of the dominant root.

Theorem 5.3 (Asymptotics). *The dominant root λ_n of $p_n(x)$ satisfies*

$$(16) \quad \lambda_n = n - \frac{4}{n} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^2}\right) \quad (n \rightarrow \infty).$$

Consequently,

$$(17) \quad 2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \sim \frac{8}{n^2 \ln n} \quad (n \rightarrow \infty).$$

Proof. Step 1: Leading correction to λ_n . Write $x = n - u$ with $u = c_1/n + O(1/n^2)$. Substituting into $p_n(x) = 0$ and collecting powers of n , the dominant balance at order n^2 gives

$$p_n(n - c_1/n) = (-c_1 + 4)n^2 + O(n).$$

Setting the n^2 coefficient to zero yields $c_1 = 4$, hence $\lambda_n = n - 4/n + O(1/n^2)$.

Verification of the n^2 balance. We expand each term of $p_n(x)$ with $x = n - c/n$:

$$\begin{aligned} x^4 &= n^4 - 4cn^2 + 6c^2 + O(1/n^2), \\ (n-1)x^3 &= n^4 - n^3 + 3cn^2 - 3cn + \dots, \\ 2x^2 &= 2n^2 - 4c + O(1/n^2), \\ (n-1)(n-4)x &= n^3 - 5n^2 + (4-c)n + O(1), \\ n(n-2) &= n^2 - 2n. \end{aligned}$$

The n^4 and n^3 terms cancel exactly; the n^2 coefficient is $-4c + 3c - 2 + 5 + 1 = -c + 4$, confirming $c = 4$.

Step 2: From λ_n to $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n)$. With $\lambda_n = n(1 - 4/n^2 + O(1/n^3))$, we have

$$\log \lambda_n = \log n + \log(1 - 4/n^2 + O(1/n^3)) = \log n - \frac{4}{n^2} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^3}\right).$$

Therefore

$$\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) = \frac{2 \log \lambda_n}{\log n} = 2 - \frac{8}{n^2 \log n} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^3 \log n}\right),$$

which gives (17). (Here \log denotes the natural logarithm.) \square

Remark 5.4 (Refined asymptotics). The next term in the expansion of λ_n can be extracted by the same method: write $x = n - 4/n + c_2/n^2$ and substitute into $p_n(x) = 0$. The n^2 coefficient was already forced to zero by $c_1 = 4$; balancing the coefficient of n (linear in c_2) gives $c_2 = 14$, so

$$\lambda_n = n - \frac{4}{n} + \frac{14}{n^2} + O(1/n^3).$$

Substituting into $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) = 2 \log \lambda_n / \log n$ and expanding, we obtain the refined gap formula

$$2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) = \frac{8}{n^2 \ln n} \left(1 - \frac{7}{2n} + O(1/n^2) \right).$$

5.4. Numerical verification. Table 2 compares the exact gap $2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n)$ with the leading asymptotic $8/(n^2 \ln n)$. The ratio converges to 1 at the expected rate $1 - O(1/n)$.

TABLE 2. Convergence of $(2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}) \cdot n^2 \ln n / 8 \rightarrow 1$.

n	$2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n)$	$8/(n^2 \ln n)$	Ratio
10	2.706×10^{-2}	3.474×10^{-2}	0.779
20	5.769×10^{-3}	6.679×10^{-3}	0.864
50	7.666×10^{-4}	8.177×10^{-4}	0.937
100	1.680×10^{-4}	1.737×10^{-4}	0.967
500	5.114×10^{-6}	5.148×10^{-6}	0.993
1000	1.154×10^{-6}	1.158×10^{-6}	0.997
10000	8.683×10^{-9}	8.687×10^{-9}	1.000

5.5. Root structure. The polynomial $p_n(x) = x^4 - (n-1)x^3 - 2x^2 - (n-1)(n-4)x + n(n-2)$ has the following properties for $n \geq 3$:

- (1) **Dominant root:** $\lambda_n \in (n-1, n)$, real and simple, with $\lambda_n = n - 4/n + O(1/n^2)$.
- (2) **Second real root:** $\mu_n \in (1, n-1)$, with $\mu_n = 1 + 2/n - 14/n^3 + O(1/n^4)$ (note that the $1/n^2$ coefficient vanishes). Existence follows from $p_n(1) = 2(n-2) > 0$ and $p_n(n-1) = -(n-2)(n^2-3n+1) < 0$ for $n \geq 3$, by the intermediate value theorem.
- (3) **Two remaining roots α_n, β_n :** by Vieta's relations,

$$\alpha_n + \beta_n = (n-1) - \lambda_n - \mu_n = -2 + \frac{2}{n} + O(1/n^2),$$

$$\alpha_n \beta_n = \frac{n(n-2)}{\lambda_n \mu_n} = n - 4 + O(1/n).$$

The pair is complex conjugate with common modulus $|\alpha_n| = |\beta_n| = \sqrt{\alpha_n \beta_n} = \sqrt{n - 2/\sqrt{n} + O(n^{-3/2})}$.

Remark 5.5 (Coefficients as functions of n). The coefficients of p_n are polynomial in n :

$$p_n(x) = x^4 - (n-1)x^3 - 2x^2 - (n^2 - 5n + 4)x + (n^2 - 2n).$$

In particular, the constant term $n^2 - 2n = n(n-2)$ is positive for $n \geq 3$, and the linear coefficient $-(n^2 - 5n + 4) = -(n-1)(n-4)$ changes sign at $n = 4$. For $n < 4$, the linear coefficient is positive; for $n > 4$ it is negative. This sign change at $n = 4$ corresponds to a subtle shift in the boundary topology (although the neighbor graph retains 6 components throughout).

5.6. Spectral gap and monopole structure. The substitution matrix M_n has characteristic polynomial $x^2 \cdot p_n(x)$, so its nonzero eigenvalues are exactly the four roots of the quartic.

Definition 5.6 (Spectral gap). Let λ_1 be the Perron eigenvalue of a boundary substitution matrix and $|\lambda_2|$ the second-largest eigenvalue modulus. The *spectral gap* is $\rho := |\lambda_2|/\lambda_1 \in [0, 1)$. We say the boundary GIFS is of *monopole type* if $\rho \ll 1$: the Perron eigenvector concentrates on a single component, meaning one boundary piece dominates the asymptotic iteration count while the remaining pieces contribute exponentially less (their shares decay as ρ^k after k substitution steps).

For the comb family in the plane,

$$\rho_n = \frac{|\lambda_2|}{\lambda_n} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} - \frac{2}{n^{3/2}} + O(n^{-5/2}) \rightarrow 0,$$

so the boundary is of monopole type for every $n \geq 3$, with a spectral gap that improves monotonically. This is a special case of a dimension-independent phenomenon; see §6.13.

Remark 5.7 (Relative measures of boundary pieces). The Perron eigenvector of M_n is proportional to the \mathcal{H}^s -measure of each boundary piece. Normalising $v_5 = 1$ and writing $\delta = \lambda_n - (n-1)$, the eigenvector equations (from the proof of Theorem 5.1) give

$$v_1 = v_2 = \frac{1}{\lambda_n}, \quad v_3 = \frac{n-2}{\lambda_n \delta}, \quad v_4 = \frac{2\lambda_n - n}{\lambda_n^2 \delta}, \quad v_6 = \frac{n-2}{\delta}.$$

Since $\lambda_n \rightarrow n$ and $\delta \rightarrow 1$, we obtain $v_6 \sim n-2$ while $v_5 = 1$ and $v_3 \approx 1$, so $v_1 = v_2 \sim 1/n$ and $v_4 \sim 1/n$ are negligible. The relative measures $w_k = v_k / \sum_j v_j$ satisfy

$$w_6 \approx 1 - \frac{2}{n}, \quad w_5 \approx w_3 \approx \frac{1}{n}, \quad w_1 = w_2, \quad w_4 = O(1/n^2).$$

Thus, for large n , the single piece B_6 carries nearly all of the \mathcal{H}^s -measure of ∂A_n : it accounts for 46% at $n = 3$, 82% at $n = 10$, and 96% at $n = 50$.

6. HIGHER-DIMENSIONAL GENERALIZATION

The comb construction extends naturally to all dimensions $d \geq 1$. In this section we define the d -dimensional comb IFS, present exact computational results for $d \leq 7$, and formulate conjectures that generalise the planar theory of Sections 3–5. The one-dimensional case $d = 1$ admits a closed-form analysis and is treated separately in §6.2; it serves as a rigorous base case for the conjectures below. All numerical results below were obtained by exact rational arithmetic using IFStile [13]; in particular, the neighbor graph computations use no floating-point approximations.

6.1. The d -dimensional comb IFS. For integers $d \geq 1$ and $n \geq 3$, let $g = C(x^d - n) \in \mathbb{Z}^{d \times d}$ be the companion matrix of $x^d - n$, with eigenvalues $n^{1/d} \zeta_d^k$ ($k = 0, \dots, d-1$, $\zeta_d = e^{2\pi i/d}$) and spectral radius $n^{1/d}$. For $d = 1$ this reduces to the scalar $g = n$.

Definition 6.1 (d -dimensional comb IFS). The d -dimensional comb IFS with parameters d and n consists of n digit maps on \mathbb{R}^d :

$$(18) \quad \begin{aligned} h_j(x) &= x + j(n-1) e_1, & j &= 0, \dots, n-2, \\ h_{n-1}(x) &= -x + (n^2 - n - 1, \underbrace{2n-3, \dots, 2n-3}_{d-1}), \end{aligned}$$

where $e_1 = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$ (for $d = 1$ the underbraced block is empty, so $h_{n-1}(x) = -x + (n^2 - n - 1)$). The attractor $A_n^{(d)} = g^{-1}(\bigcup_{j=0}^{n-1} h_j(A_n^{(d)}))$.

For $d = 2$ this recovers Definition 2.1; for $d = 1$, see §6.2. The off-axis translation $2n-3 = 2(n-1) - 1$ is the same in all $d-1$ transverse coordinates.

Remark 6.2 (Motivation of the construction). The construction of Definition 6.1 was discovered by a systematic IFStile [13] search over self-similar IFS minimising the number of boundary components, and its particular form can be motivated from first principles only in part.

- *Expansion.* Requiring n digit maps of equal contraction ratio $n^{-1/d}$ and integer-matrix expansion forces, up to similarity, the companion matrix of a monic integer polynomial with constant term $\pm n$; the minimal such polynomial is $x^d - n$, used here.
- *Digit residues.* By Proposition 2.3, the digit set must project to a complete residue system modulo $g\mathbb{Z}^d \cong \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$. Taking $n-1$ aligned digits at $0, n-1, 2(n-1), \dots, (n-2)(n-1)$ along e_1 covers residues $\{0, -1, -2, \dots, -(n-2)\} \pmod{n}$; a single additional digit with residue ± 1 completes the system for every n simultaneously, which explains why the same combinatorial pattern works for all n .
- *Transverse offset.* The specific value $2n-3$ of the transverse translation in h_{n-1} , as well as the choice of $-I$ rather than $+I$ for its linear part, were selected empirically to minimise the neighbor graph. A first-principles derivation of these choices — and a proof that the resulting graph complexity is the smallest possible in this expansion class — remains open (see §7).

We verify that $A_n^{(d)}$ is a tile by applying Proposition 2.3 in dimension d .

Corollary 6.3. For every $d \geq 1$ and $n \geq 3$, the attractor $A_n^{(d)}$ of Definition 6.1 tiles \mathbb{R}^d and $\dim_{\text{H}}(A_n^{(d)}) = d$.

Proof. The symmetry group $P = \{I, -I\}$ centralizes every matrix. The digit maps of Definition 6.1 have the form $h_j(x) = s_j x + d_j$ with $s_j = I$ for $j < n-1$ and $s_{n-1} = -I$. Since $s_j(x + s_j^{-1}d_j) = s_j x + d_j$, rewriting in the form (4) gives digit vectors $v_j = s_j^{-1}d_j$:

$$v_j = j(n-1) e_1 \quad (j = 0, \dots, n-2), \quad v_{n-1} = -d_{n-1}.$$

The companion matrix $g = C(x^d - n)$ satisfies $|\det g| = n$, and $g\mathbb{Z}^d$ is spanned by $\{e_2, \dots, e_d, ne_1\}$ (since $ge_k = e_{k+1}$ for $k < d$ and $ge_d = ne_1$), so $\mathbb{Z}^d/g\mathbb{Z}^d \cong \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ via the first coordinate modulo n . The first coordinates of the digit vectors modulo n

are: $j(n-1) \equiv -j$ for $j = 0, \dots, n-2$, and $-(n^2-n-1) \equiv 1$ for $j = n-1$. Thus the residues are $\{0, n-1, n-2, \dots, 2, 1\} = \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$, a complete system. The result follows from Proposition 2.3. \square

Remark 6.4 (Bounding parallelepiped). The Hutchinson operator $F = \bigcup_j f_j$ maps the d -dimensional comb box

$$R_d = [0, 2n-3]^{d-1} \times [0, n-1-1/n]$$

into itself: $F(R_d) \subseteq R_d$ for every $d \geq 1$ and $n \geq 3$. This generalises Lemma 3.1 ($d = 2$); for $d = 1$ it gives the bounding interval $R_1 = [0, n-1-1/n]$. Indeed, $g^{-1}(y_1, \dots, y_d) = (y_2, \dots, y_d, y_1/n)$ (reducing to $g^{-1}(y) = y/n$ when $d = 1$), so $g^{-1}(R_d) = [0, 2n-3]^{d-2} \times [0, n-1-1/n] \times [0, (2n-3)/n]$. Adding the spine translations $j(n-1)/n \cdot e_d$ ($j = 0, \dots, n-2$) fills the last coordinate of R_d up to $(n^2-n-1)/n = n-1-1/n$ and leaves the first $d-1$ coordinates inside R_d . The tooth piece $f_{n-1}(R_d)$ fits in the corner $[0, 2n-3]^{d-2} \times [n-2+1/n, 2n-3] \times [n-3+2/n, n-1-1/n]$ (the first interval is absent when $d \leq 2$, the second when $d = 1$).

Consequently $A_n^{(d)} = \bigcap_{k \geq 0} F^k(R_d)$ is a monotone intersection of compact PL sets. This is the natural starting point for any future ball-likeness proof (see §7).

Figure 8 shows the attractor $A_5^{(3)}$ in dimension $d = 3$.

FIGURE 8. The 3-dimensional comb tile $A_5^{(3)}$ ($d = 3$, $n = 5$), rendered in the real Jordan basis of the companion matrix $g = C(x^3 - 5)$.

Remark 6.5 (IFStile program for $d = 3$). The 3-dimensional comb tile can be rendered in IFStile [13] using the following program (shown for $n = 5$):

```
@
$dim=3
$subspace=[g,0,1]
g=$companion([-5,0,0])
h1=[4,0,0]
h2=[8,0,0]
```

$h_3=[12,0,0]$
 $h_4=[19,7,7]*-1$
 $A=g^{-1}*(1|h_1|h_2|h_3|h_4)*A$

Here $\$companion([-5,0,0])$ creates the companion matrix of x^3-5 , and $\$subspace=[g,0,1]$ projects from \mathbb{R}^3 to the eigenbasis of g : the real eigenvalue $5^{1/3}$ (index 0, one dimension) and the complex conjugate pair $5^{1/3}\zeta_3^{\pm 1}$ (index 1, two dimensions). For general $n \geq 3$, replace -5 with $-n$ in the companion matrix, adjust the translations to $h_j = [j(n-1), 0, 0]$ for $j = 1, \dots, n-2$, and set $h_{n-1} = [n^2-n-1, 2n-3, 2n-3] \cdot (-I_3)$.

6.2. The closed-form case $d = 1$. Before stating the general conjectures, we analyse the one-dimensional case in full. Unlike the cases $d \geq 2$, both the neighbor graph and the dominant root admit closed-form expressions, providing a rigorous base case for the conjectures formulated below.

At $d = 1$, Definition 6.1 reads: scalar expansion $g = n$ and digit maps

$$h_j(x) = x + j(n-1) \quad (j = 0, \dots, n-2), \quad h_{n-1}(x) = -x + (n^2-n-1),$$

so $f_j(x) = h_j(x)/n$ for $j < n-1$ and $f_{n-1}(x) = (-x + n^2-n-1)/n$. All contractions have ratio $1/n$.

Proposition 6.6 (Complete analysis at $d = 1$). *For every $n \geq 3$:*

- (1) $A_n^{(1)}$ has positive Lebesgue measure and satisfies the OSC.
- (2) The neighbor graph has exactly two non-trivial types,

$$\sigma_1(x) = -x + (2n-3), \quad \sigma_2(x) = -x + (n-2).$$

- (3) The substitution matrix and its characteristic polynomial are

$$(19) \quad M_n^{(1)} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ n-2 & n-1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad q_n^{(1)}(x) = x^2 - (n-1)x - (n-2).$$

Proof. Step 1 (OSC). The digits $v_j = s_j^{-1}h_j(0) \pmod n$ form a complete residue system: for $j < n-1$ we have $s_j = I$ and $v_j = j(n-1) \equiv -j \pmod n$, while $s_{n-1} = -I$ and $v_{n-1} = -(n^2-n-1) \equiv 1 \pmod n$, so $\{v_0, \dots, v_{n-1}\} \equiv \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\} \pmod n$. Proposition 2.3 now gives $\mu(A_n^{(1)}) > 0$ and the OSC.

Step 2 (bounding interval). Let $L = (n^2-n-1)/n = n-1 - 1/n$ and $I = [0, L]$. A direct check shows $f_j(I) \subset I$ for every j : for $j < n-1$ the maximum of f_j on I is $(L + j(n-1))/n$, which at $j = n-2$ equals $(n-1)^2(2n-1)/(n^2(n-1))$ and is bounded by L since $(n-1)^2 \geq 0$; for f_{n-1} the maximum is $(n^2-n-1)/n = L$. Hence $A_n^{(1)} \subset I$. Consequently, if $\sigma = f_i^{-1}f_j$ is a neighbor type (i.e., $\sigma(A) \cap A \neq \emptyset$), its translation component lies in $[-2L, 2L]$.

Step 3 (level-1 neighbors). Enumerate the ordered pairs (i, j) with $i \neq j$ by the orientations of s_i and s_j :

- *Both spine* ($i, j < n-1$): $\sigma(x) = x + (j-i)(n-1)$, translation $t = (j-i)(n-1)$ of modulus $\geq n-1$. Since $n-1 > L$, the shifted interval $I + t$ intersects I only when $|t| < n-1 - 1/n$, which fails. No contribution.
- *Tooth/spine* ($i = n-1, j < n-1$): $\sigma(x) = -x + t$ with $t = (n-1)(n-j) - 1$. The admissibility $0 \leq t \leq 2L$ forces $n - j \leq (2n-1)/(n-1) < 3$, i.e., $j \in \{n-2, n-1\}$; excluding $j = n-1$ leaves $j = n-2, t = 2n-3$: the type σ_1 .
- *Spine/tooth* ($i < n-1, j = n-1$): symmetric under $\sigma \mapsto \sigma^{-1}$ (and $\sigma_1^{-1} = \sigma_1$), giving the same type σ_1 .

Level-1 thus yields a single type σ_1 .

Step 4 (substitution row for σ_1). For each ordered pair (j, k) compute $\sigma' = f_j^{-1}\sigma_1 f_k$.

- $j, k < n-1$: $\sigma'(x) = -x + 2n^2 - 3n - (j+k)(n-1)$. Admissibility forces $j+k \geq 2n-3$, but $j+k \leq 2(n-2) = 2n-4$; no contribution.
- $j = n-1$ or $k = n-1$ (exactly one): σ' is a translation $x \mapsto x \pm (n-1-m)(n-1)$ for $m \in \{0, \dots, n-2\}$; the only admissible value is $\pm(n-1)$, and $A \pm (n-1)$ is disjoint from A (as in the spine/spine case). No contribution.
- $j = k = n-1$: $\sigma'(x) = -x + (n-2) = \sigma_2$. This is a new type, attached to σ_1 by a single edge.

This yields the first row $[0, 1]$ of $M_n^{(1)}$.

Step 5 (substitution row for σ_2). Similarly decompose $\sigma'' = f_j^{-1}\sigma_2 f_k$.

- $j, k < n-1$: $\sigma''(x) = -x + n^2 - 2n - (j+k)(n-1)$, admissible iff $n-3 \leq j+k \leq n-2$.
 - $j+k = n-3$: $t = 2n-3 = \sigma_1$, attained by $n-2$ pairs.
 - $j+k = n-2$: $t = n-2 = \sigma_2$, attained by $n-1$ pairs.
- $j = n-1$ or $k = n-1$ (exactly one): σ'' is a translation whose admissible value $\pm(n-1)$ gives pieces disjoint from A (as in Step 4).
- $j = k = n-1$: $\sigma''(x) = -x + (n^2-2)$ with $t = n^2 - 2 > 2L$ for $n \geq 3$, not a neighbor.

The second row is therefore $[n-2, n-1]$. Since both rows reference only σ_1 and σ_2 , the neighbor graph is closed: no further types arise, completing the enumeration and proving (19). \square

Corollary 6.7 (Asymptotics at $d = 1$). *The dominant eigenvalue λ_n of $M_n^{(1)}$ satisfies*

$$(20) \quad \lambda_n = \frac{(n-1) + \sqrt{n^2 + 2n - 7}}{2} = n - \frac{2}{n} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^2}\right),$$

and, consequently,

$$(21) \quad 1 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n^{(1)}) = \frac{2}{n^2 \ln n} (1 + O(1/n)).$$

Proof. The closed form follows from $q_n^{(1)}(x) = 0$ via the quadratic formula. Writing $\lambda_n = n + a/n + O(1/n^2)$ and substituting into $\lambda_n^2 - (n-1)\lambda_n - (n-2) = 0$, the coefficient of n^0 yields $a + 2 = 0$, hence $a = -2$. Then $\log(\lambda_n/n) = \log(1 - 2/n^2 + O(1/n^3)) = -2/n^2 + O(1/n^3)$, so

$$1 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n^{(1)}) = 1 - \frac{\log \lambda_n}{\log n} = \frac{2}{n^2 \ln n} (1 + O(1/n)). \quad \square$$

Remark 6.8 (Consistency with the conjectures). Both predictions of Conjectures 6.9 and 6.11 (stated below) hold at $d = 1$:

- $p(1) = 2$, the initial condition of the recurrence (22) in Conjecture 6.9.
- The leading coefficient $c_1^{(1)} = 2$ in expansion (21) matches the predicted $2d^2$ of Conjecture 6.11 at $d = 1$.

Topology. The 1-dimensional analog of ball-likeness is connectedness. For $n \geq 3$, the first Hutchinson iterate of the bounding interval $[0, n-1-1/n]$ leaves $n-3$ residual gaps (each of length $1/n^2$) between consecutive spine intervals, none of

which is covered by the single tooth image; these gaps persist under iteration and yield a dense family of gaps at every scale $1/n^{2^k}$. More precisely, $A_n^{(1)}$ is a *cantorval* in the sense of Guthrie–Nymann [11]: a compact subset of \mathbb{R} with positive Lebesgue measure and without isolated points, which is neither a finite union of intervals nor a Cantor set, and such that both endpoints of every gap are accumulation points of other gaps. In particular, $A_n^{(1)}$ is not connected, so the topological analog of Theorem 4.4 fails in dimension one, while the algebraic and metric statements (OSC, substitution spectrum, asymptotic boundary dimension) continue to hold unchanged. This singles out the connectedness condition as the essential non-trivial ingredient of the disk-like theorem in $d = 2$.

6.3. Boundary component count.

Conjecture 6.9 (Boundary components). *For every $d \geq 1$ and $n \geq 3$, the number $p(d)$ of boundary components of $A_n^{(d)}$ depends only on d , not on n , and satisfies the linear recurrence*

$$(22) \quad p(d) = 2p(d-1) + p(d-2) + 2, \quad d \geq 2,$$

with initial values $p(0) = 0$ and $p(1) = 2$ (Proposition 6.6); equivalently, $p(2) = 6$ (Theorem 3.3).

TABLE 3. Boundary component count $p(d)$ and reduced characteristic polynomial degree $\deg q_n^{(d)}$ of the d -dimensional comb tile. For $d \leq 5$ the data are verified for all $n = 3, \dots, 10$; for $d = 6$ and $d = 7$ they are verified at $n = 3$. Empirically $\deg q_n^{(d)} = p(d) - p(d-1)$.

d	$p(d)$	$\deg q_n^{(d)}$	Status
1	2	2	Proposition 6.6
2	6	4	Theorem 3.3, Theorem 5.1
3	16	10	$n = 3, \dots, 10$
4	40	24	$n = 3, \dots, 10$
5	98	58	$n = 3, \dots, 10$
6	238	140	$n = 3$
7	576	338	$n = 3$

The sequence $(p(d))_{d \geq 0} = 0, 2, 6, 16, 40, 98, 238, 576, 1392, \dots$ is OEIS A265278 [20] (shifted by one). Solving the recurrence (22) yields the closed form

$$(23) \quad p(d) = \frac{1}{2}((1+\sqrt{2})^{d+1} + (1-\sqrt{2})^{d+1}) - 1.$$

Asymptotically $p(d) \sim (1+\sqrt{2})^{d+1}/2$, so the graph complexity grows exponentially with the ambient dimension but remains independent of n .

Remark 6.10 (Combinatorial origin). The same integer sequence enumerates several families of pattern-avoiding combinatorial structures: reverse double lists avoiding a length-3 pattern [5], Cayley permutations [9], and weakly single-peaked weak orderings with a unique maximum [4]. This suggests that the $p(d)$ boundary pieces may admit a combinatorial description, although no direct bijection is currently known. A structural hint is visible in the substitution matrix: a posteriori computation

shows that $p(d-1)$ of the $p(d)$ pieces correspond to zero eigenvalues (see §6.4), so these pieces appear “inherited” from the $(d-1)$ -dimensional structure, while the remaining $p(d) - p(d-1)$ pieces arise from interaction with the single transverse map.

6.4. Reduced characteristic polynomial. For each d , the boundary substitution matrix $M_n^{(d)}$ has size $p(d) \times p(d)$. Computations show that its characteristic polynomial has exactly $p(d-1)$ zero eigenvalues, so the reduced polynomial $q_n^{(d)}(\lambda)$ has degree $p(d) - p(d-1)$ (cf. Table 3). Its dominant root λ_n determines the boundary dimension:

$$(24) \quad \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n^{(d)}) = \frac{d \log \lambda_n}{\log n}.$$

For $d = 2$, $q_n^{(2)} = p_n$ is the quartic (12). For $d = 3$ and $d = 4$, all coefficients of $q_n^{(d)}$ have been determined as explicit polynomials in n (of degree at most 5 and 12 respectively) by fitting data for $n = 3, \dots, 20$ and verifying the result for all n in that range. For $d = 5$ the degree is 58; boundary polynomials have been computed for $n = 3, \dots, 10$, but the parametric form is not yet determined.

6.5. Asymptotic boundary dimension.

Conjecture 6.11 (Asymptotic rate). *For every fixed $d \geq 1$,*

$$(25) \quad d - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n^{(d)}) \sim \frac{2d^2}{n^2 \ln n} \quad (n \rightarrow \infty).$$

Equivalently, the dominant root satisfies $\lambda_n = n - 2d/n + O(1/n^2)$.

For $d = 1$ this is Corollary 6.7 ($2 \cdot 1 = 2$). For $d = 2$ this is Theorem 5.3 ($2 \cdot 4 = 8$). For $d = 3$ and $d = 4$, the explicit parametric polynomials $q_n^{(3)}$ and $q_n^{(4)}$ yield exact dominant roots for all n , and the normalised gap $(d - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}) \cdot n^2 \ln n / (2d^2)$ converges to 1 as predicted.

Table 4 lists boundary dimensions for selected values of n in dimensions $d = 3$ and 5.

TABLE 4. Boundary dimension $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n^{(d)})$ of the d -dimensional comb tile (compare with Table 1 for $d = 2$).

n	$d = 3$	$d = 5$
3	2.471	4.464
5	2.807	4.762
7	2.902	4.856
10	2.953	4.919
20	2.989	—

Remark 6.12 (Topological conjecture). In dimension $d \geq 3$ the analog of the disk-like property is *ball-likeness* (homeomorphy to the closed d -ball). No effective criterion comparable to [6] is available for $d \geq 3$. We conjecture that $A_n^{(d)}$ is ball-like for all $d \geq 2$ and all $n \geq 3$.

Remark 6.13 (Monopole structure in higher dimensions). The planar bound $\rho_n^{(2)} = O(1/\sqrt{n})$ admits a dimension-dependent generalisation. Numerical computation gives

$$(26) \quad \rho_n^{(d)} \sim c_d n^{-1/d} \quad (n \rightarrow \infty),$$

with c_d bounded (verified for $d \leq 5$; $c_1 = 1$, $c_2 \rightarrow 1$, $c_3 \approx 1.06$, $c_4 \approx 1.16$, $c_5 \approx 1.18$). The exponent $1/d$ matches the contraction ratio of the IFS ($n^{-1/d}$ = spectral radius of g^{-1}): the secondary eigenvalues grow as $|\lambda_2| \sim n^{(d-1)/d}$, while the Perron eigenvalue grows linearly. In particular, $\rho_n^{(d)} \rightarrow 0$ for every fixed $d \geq 1$ but the spectral gap weakens as d increases.

For $d = 1$, the explicit 2×2 matrix $M_n^{(1)}$ of Proposition 6.6 satisfies $\det M_n^{(1)} = -(n-2)$, so $|\lambda_2^{(1)}| = (n-2)/\lambda_n \rightarrow 1$ and $\rho_n^{(1)} = (n-2)/\lambda_n^2 \sim 1/n$.

For $d = 2$, Schur's inequality $\lambda_n^2 + |\lambda_2|^2 \leq \|M_n^{(2)}\|_F^2$ combined with the explicit form of M_n ($\|M_n\|_F^2 = (n-1)^2 + O(n)$) and Theorem 5.3 ($\lambda_n = n - 4/n + O(1/n^2)$) gives $|\lambda_2| = O(\sqrt{n})$ and hence $\rho_n^{(2)} = O(1/\sqrt{n})$, agreeing with (26).

For $d \geq 3$, the bound (26) remains conjectural.

7. OPEN QUESTIONS AND OUTLOOK

The comb family combines three features which, taken together, appear to be new: bounded neighbor-graph complexity, disk-likeness for all n , and boundary dimension tending to 2. We close with a summary of the main phenomena uncovered, followed by a list of questions that remain open.

Summary of main phenomena.

- *Constant graph with $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \rightarrow 2$.* The comb family provides the first explicit construction (to our knowledge) of an infinite parametric family of self-similar tiles with $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \rightarrow 2$ and *bounded* neighbor graph complexity: exactly 6 components for all $n \geq 3$ (Remark 3.4). This complements Keesling's examples [14], where $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A)$ can be made arbitrarily close to 2 but the graph complexity grows without bound.
- *Source of the rate $2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \sim 8/(n^2 \ln n)$.* The rate is determined by the quartic $p_n(x)$. Indeed, $p_n(n) = 2n(2n-3)$ while the product of the three non-dominant conjugates at n grows as $\sim n^3$, so $n - \lambda_n \sim 4/n$ and the rate $8/(n^2 \ln n)$ follows directly.
- *Universality of the combinatorial pattern.* The disk-like property (Theorem 4.4) is proved via the criterion of Loricant, Luo and Thuswaldner [6]: the triple intersection structure cycles with period 2 independently of n , mirroring the constancy of the neighbor graph (Theorem 3.3). In both results only the translations in the neighbor maps change with n , while the combinatorial pattern is universal.

Open questions.

- (1) **Ball-likeness in dimension $d \geq 3$.** The d -dimensional generalisation (Section 6) preserves OSC and the substitution-matrix structure, but the topological analog of the disk-like property remains fully open for $d \geq 3$: is $A_n^{(d)}$ homeomorphic to the closed d -ball? The $d = 1$ case is settled negatively (Proposition 6.6: $A_n^{(1)}$ is a cantorval), and $d = 2$ is settled positively (Theorem 4.4).

- (2) **Conjectures on boundary structure for $d \geq 3$.** The recurrence for the boundary component count (Conjecture 6.9) and the asymptotic rate $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n^{(d)}) \sim d - \alpha_d/(n^2 \ln n)$ (Conjecture 6.11) are verified by exact computation for $d \leq 7$, but proofs in full generality are open. Note that the two-step recurrence (22) is anchored precisely on the dimensions treated rigorously in this paper: $d = 1$ (Proposition 6.6) and $d = 2$ (Theorem 3.3). A proof of the inductive step $d-2, d-1 \Rightarrow d$ would therefore give the full sequence of boundary structures.
- (3) **Combinatorial origin of A265278.** The sequence $p(d) = 0, 2, 6, 16, 40, 98, \dots$ of boundary component counts coincides with OEIS A265278 [20], which also enumerates reverse double lists avoiding a length-3 pattern [5], certain quasitrivial semigroups [4], and Cayley permutations [9]. Is there a direct bijection between any of these combinatorial families and the boundary components of the d -dimensional comb?
- (4) **Role of digit non-collinearity.** The non-collinearity of the digit set is essential for $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \rightarrow 2$: a rectangle $1 \times \sqrt{n}$ tiled by n rotated copies of itself is disk-like with n pieces of ratio $1/\sqrt{n}$, but all digits are collinear and $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A) = 1$ for all n . A precise quantitative formulation — minimum transverse displacement required to force $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n) \rightarrow 2$ — is open.
- (5) **Optimality and enumeration at small n .** For each $n \geq 3$, classify all disk-like self-similar tiles with n maps whose boundary dimension exceeds $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n)$. The comb tile need not be optimal within its class: already for $n = 3$ the twin dragon (2 maps, $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A) \approx 1.524$) exceeds the comb value $\dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_3) \approx 1.453$, albeit with a different number of maps. A systematic search over all admissible orientation assignments could resolve optimality for small n .
- (6) **Improving the rate.** Is there a disk-like family on \mathbb{R}^2 with bounded graph complexity for which $2 - \dim_{\mathbb{H}}(\partial A_n)$ decays faster than $8/(n^2 \ln n)$? By the argument above, this would require a characteristic polynomial satisfying $|p(n)| = o(n^2)$.
- (7) **First-principles derivation of the transverse offset.** The transverse translation $2n-3$ in h_{n-1} and the use of $-I$ as its linear part were selected empirically (via an IFStile search) to minimise the neighbor graph. Is the resulting 6-component graph optimal within the expansion class $g = C(x^d - n)$? More generally, can the entire construction of Definition 6.1 be characterised as the unique (up to symmetry) choice minimising graph complexity among self-similar IFS with expansion g and n digits?

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